

A New Perspective on Opportunistic Drug-Facilitated Sexual Assault on Females

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Abstract

In this article, a unique approach was used to study the victimization of women by opportunistic drug-facilitated sexual assault in leisure environments. The evidence from both forensic case studies and contextual studies about sexual interrelation and drug use was analyzed using a multifocal analytical strategy based on an intersectional gender-sensitive approach. The hegemonic recreational nightlife paradigm intersects with social changes that have an impact on consuming habits and sexual behavior as part of the victimization process. However, victims encounter a variety of circumstances that make it challenging for them to recognize themselves as such. The societal skepticism that victims experience is exacerbated by widespread beliefs about the victimization process, which result from gender-based double standards that set expectations for what is expected of women in terms of drug use and sexual activity. The victims frequently suffer from amnesia, lack of physical injuries, and mental suffering, which makes it challenging for them to self-identify as sexual assault victims and to report the incident. As a result, there is an urgent need for public health to adopt a new perspective on how women are victimized by opportunistic drug-facilitated sexual assault in contexts of leisure, able to raise awareness of the gravity of this form of sexual violence. In order to assist victims in acknowledging their situation, filing a complaint, and getting the treatment they need, society must admit the presence of this problem within itself. Lack of this social support encourages victimization to continue, heightening the danger of trapping victims in cycles of re-victimization and encouraging both underreporting and ineffective coping mechanisms. Other recommendations include the use of the term "take advantage," the development of specific criminal approaches, and the in-depth knowledge of the phenomenon through victimization surveys. These recommendations center on the need to raise awareness of the severity of female victimization by opportunistic drug-facilitated sexual assault in leisure contexts. These processes are essential for creating evidence-based, realistically targeted preventive actions.

Keywords: Drug-facilitated sexual assault (DFSA) • Sexual violence • Date-rape drugs • Young women

Introduction

Sexual violence is a serious global public health issue that primarily affects women. It includes any unwelcome sexual acts, attempts, statements, and insinuations. Since the age of fifteen, one in ten European women have experienced some kind of sexual abuse, and one in twenty have been sexually assaulted. In the past year, 2.0% of women have experienced sexual assault in some way, which is fairly close to the 14% of

women in Spain who have encountered sexual violence at some point in their lives. Additionally, research from Spain and other nations confirms that young women experience the highest incidence of sexual violence. The complex nature of sexual assault includes, among other things, the use of psychoactive substances, including prescription and illicit medications, medical treatments, and other substances. Psychoactive chemicals have frequently been used to mediate sexual intercourse throughout history [1-2]. However, if social changes take place and have an impact on purchasing habits and sexual contact, this mediation may need to be modified. With the gender gap narrowing in recent decades, numerous studies have noted considerable changes in female spending patterns, particularly among younger women. The phenomena of substance-mediated sexual violence, also known as drug-facilitated sexual assault, is a result of the interaction between sexual violence and the use of psychoactive substances. 11% of American women over the age of eighteen have been sexually assaulted while under the influence of alcohol or drugs at some point in their life, and 1% have happened within the past year. In the UK, 38% of victims who indicated they had been raped at least once before the age of 16 reported being drunk at the time of their most recent rape. Depending on the attacker's modus operandi, DFSA victims might be classified as either proactive or opportunistic. In opportunistic assaults, the attacker takes advantage of the victim's voluntary intoxication-induced condition of incapacity [3-5].

Drug in a sneaky or coerced manner to the victim. Case studies in numerous nations have shown that young women are particularly affected by DFSA victimization, often as a result of opportunistic assaults following voluntary intoxication. The DFSA has identified youth leisure as the primary context of victimization, however numerous writers call for more research. The hunting model states that sexual opportunism fits the typical conduct of sexual attackers who choose their victims based on their level of vulnerability or their capacity to fend off an attack. Initiatives by the DFSA's criminal prosecution reflect the concern of the world community for the phenomenon. Drug-facilitated rape is classified as an injury act under the International Classification of Crime for Statistical Purposes, and official guidelines for the forensic examination of substances that enabled sexual assault have been released. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development also lists the eradication of sexual violence against women as one of the major global challenges [6]. To meet this problem, it is currently necessary to identify and recognize all types of sexual violence. The inability to identify a particular type of violence makes it more difficult to address it and encourages its continuation. No one will be left behind is the exact motto of the 2030 Agenda in this regard. Despite being the primary kind of victimization in the DFSA phenomenon, opportunism is not sufficiently studied or understood. This circumstance most often arises from a focus of attention that has wandered from the main reality. In this regard, a number of studies warn against the proactive version of DFSA receiving frightening media coverage that diverts focus from opportunism. Therefore, there is an urgent need for an adequate study and identification of victimization by opportunistic DFSA and the challenges experienced by victims. The setting in Spain, where the hegemonic recreational nightlife model predominates and combines a pattern of leisure focused on the culture of self-intoxication with a model of immediate sexuality, provides a useful foundation for this goal. In order to draw conclusions that are applicable to other communities that share the same recreational model, the analysis can help to better understand an issue that arises from the confluence of global influencing elements, such as the use of psychoactive substances and sexual violence. In-depth knowledge of the victimization by opportunistic DFSA, its causes, and how it endures in society is the goal of this study. To promote the adoption of a fresh perspective on the issue and raise public awareness of the seriousness of female victimization by this type of sexual violence [7-10].

Conclusion

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wandered from the main reality. In this regard, a number of studies warn against the proactive version of DFSA receiving frightening media coverage that diverts focus from opportunism. Therefore, there is an urgent need for an adequate study and identification of victimization by opportunistic DFSA and the challenges experienced by victims. The setting in Spain, where the hegemonic recreational nightlife model predominates and combines a pattern of leisure focused on the culture of self-intoxication with a model of immediate sexuality, provides a useful foundation for this goal. In order to draw conclusions that are applicable to other communities that share the same recreational model, the analysis can help to better understand an issue that arises from the confluence of global influencing elements, such as the use of psychoactive substances and sexual violence. In-depth knowledge of the victimization by opportunistic DFSA, its causes, and how it endures in society is the goal of this study. To promote the adoption of a fresh perspective on the issue and raise public awareness of the seriousness of female victimization by this type of sexual violence. 11% of American women over the age of eighteen have been sexually assaulted while under the influence of alcohol or drugs at some point in their life, and 1% have happened within the past year. In the UK, 38% of victims who indicated they had been raped at least once before the age of 16 reported being drunk at the time of their most recent rape. Depending on the attacker's modus operandi, DFSA victims might be classified as either proactive or opportunistic. In opportunistic assaults, the attacker takes advantage of the victim's voluntary intoxication-induced condition of incapacity drug in a sneaky or coerced manner to the victim. Case studies in numerous nations have shown that young women are particularly affected by DFSA victimization, often as a result of opportunistic assaults following voluntary intoxication.

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Finally, in-depth information is necessary to solve the issue effectively. In this regard, the use of victimization surveys is urged in order to better understand the true scope of the problem, which is required for the creation of well-targeted, evidence-based preventive actions that are realistic.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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